

Web of Things Interoperability for the Arrowhead Framework

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Abstract—Defined as the ability for a system to exchange data with another system and consume data from another system, interoperability is a property that most distributed system developers tend to satisfy when designing new systems. In the IoT domain, the WoT W3C standard has been proposed to enable interoperability between devices and platforms.

The Arrowhead framework has been implemented to ease IoT automation with the objective to enable IoT interoperability in this domain.

This paper discusses how the W3C Web of Things standard can help the IoT automation framework Arrowhead in achieving the interoperability.

Index Terms—Arrowhead Framework, Web of Things (WoT), IoT, Thing Directory, Thing Description

I. INTRODUCTION

The Arrowhead framework [1] applies the Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) [2] to the industrial domain [3], by having distributed systems designated as service providers making their services known to services from systems designated as consumers, which have a way to discover and consume them. The Arrowhead framework is currently used to support application development in many business domains such as industrial processes and manufacturing [4], Smart Buildings and infrastructures [5], Energy production and Virtual Markets of Energy [6].

Interoperability is essential in an distributed embedded environment, especially required between devices, from a device to a platform, or between applications. Even though Arrowhead succeeded in enabling interoperability in the industrial context [7]–[10], and it allows the creation of Systems of Things (SoTs) that interact together but are not dependent on each other, there are application areas such as the Internet of Things (IoT) that started their journey way more in the past, and that gave birth to a plethora of middleware and approaches.

The Web of Things (WoT) [11] standard has been proposed to create interoperability when using IoT devices and IoT platforms. It is gaining acceptance and it is considering a standard in the IoT domain. However, it is not natively compliant with the Arrowhead Framework.

Compatibility between the Arrowhead approach and WoT will push the Arrowhead Framework one step forward towards being the interoperability champion in the industry. In fact, for systems to be integrated into the Arrowhead architecture [12], there is no explicit requirement about the nature of the system or the protocol it communicates into, except for

the interaction with the Arrowhead mandatory core systems (see Section II-A). This work proposes a design to allow an Arrowhead-compliant system to discover and access the services from a WoT Thing, and the implementation of a core system (Thing Directory System) that supports our strategy.

Previous work [13] considered to augment WoT Things with an Arrowhead Thing Mirror to let the Things serve Arrowhead HTTP requests, and complemented it with a crawler polling the Thing Directory (see Section II-B) to populate the Arrowhead Service Registry (see Section II-A). Our solution, on the other hand, does not employ polling, does not require Things to have an Arrowhead Thing Mirror, and notices that the best security for both Arrowhead and WoT is based on the Java Web Token (JWT) [14], leading to a proposal for a common security approach.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the Arrowhead Framework and the Web of Things, whose interoperability is discussed in Section III, which also presents the architecture for the Thing Directory System. Section IV describes the implementation of the Thing Directory System, and Section V presents an application use case. We draw conclusions and present possible future works in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

This section gives more details about the Arrowhead Framework and the Web of Things.

A. Arrowhead framework

The Arrowhead Framework [1] is an implementation of a SOA platform oriented to microservices and based on the concept of local clouds [15]. In the Arrowhead vision, all software systems interact by means of services and are run on devices. A local cloud is defined as a logical organization of systems that can operate independently and securely as per the SOA paradigm. The local cloud always provides several essential core services that enable fundamental service-oriented properties such as service registration, service discovery, authentication and authorization, the orchestration of SoTs, and the support for automation system requirements such as real-time properties, security, safety, and engineering automation functionalities.

The Arrowhead Framework defines a set of core systems to establish a local cloud, where three are mandatory and required

in all local clouds (ServiceRegistry system, Authorization system, and Orchestration system). The ServiceRegistry system permits a service provider to publish its service instances and make them discoverable by service consumers. The Authorization system manages security, and the Orchestration system enables orchestration of which service instance a consumer shall consume. Another (non-mandatory) core system is the SystemRegistry system, which collects data regarding which device hosts a given system.

With regards to security, Arrowhead makes use of three different security levels, namely `not_secure`, `certificate` and `token` [16]. Except for the first level, the other ones make use of a certificate hierarchy founded on the the public key of the Arrowhead local cloud hosting the systems. In particular, the token of Arrowhead's `token` security is fundamentally a JWT token [14]. The token creates a session control functionality, and it validates each access of a service provider, specifying which system can access it. It considers also inter-cloud access, and in fact the token creation happens during the orchestration phase, and it is bargained between the core systems of the clouds of the service provider and service consumer.

B. Web of Things

The W3C Web of Things standard has been proposed to enable interoperability between the different platforms and applications in the IoT domain. The WoT standard provides an architecture [17] that has been designed to describe the things (abstraction of a physical or virtual entity) and to improve their usability while enabling interoperability.

The architecture is composed of 4 building blocks, which are formally specified:

- The WoT Thing Description (TD) [18] is a JSON format that describes thing metadata, properties, protocol supported, and the different interfaces.
- The WoT Binding Templates [19] use a set of information to describe the communication protocols supported by a Thing. It enables a client to adapt to the underlying protocol the thing can use.
- The WoT Scripting API [20] provides a convenient way to implement WoT applications that describe how to work (discover, operate, and expose) with a thing using its TD. It can also be used in gateways to extend WoT support to new types of endpoints.
- The WoT Security and Privacy Guidelines [21] define the general security requirements for the WoT.

Different implementations of the standard have been proposed with the promising ones the `node-wot`¹ implementation and the Mozilla implementation².

The fundamental building block of the WoT architecture is the Thing Description (see Figure 1), composed by: metadata to help describe the behavior of the Thing; Interaction Affordances specifying the interfaces to the thing; data schemas that

Fig. 1. Architectural Aspects of a Thing [17]

represent the data exchanged with the Thing; security configurations represent how privacy and security are supported by the thing; finally, some links for the protocols supported are listed.

The WoT architecture defines a directory service for TDs called Thing Directory, which provides a Web interface to register them and make metadata of the things available to applications. A client application can then find the metadata needed to communicate with a thing by querying the Thing Directory. With regards to security, it is defined per-thing [18]. The most interesting security schemes supported by the standard are the cheapest two (`NoSecurityScheme` and `BasicSecurityScheme`) and the most flexible and secure one (`BearerSecurityScheme`), which are then augmented by means of a TLS tunnel that allows for privacy of the communication between service consumer and producer, given that the TLS' certificate is signed by a trusted party [22].

The `NoSecurityScheme` scheme considers that any request that gets to the service provider has to be served. The `BasicSecurityScheme` scheme [23] requires a plaintext username and password sent together with the request. For example, username and password can be transported in the header or in the body of a POST request, and they should be protected by a TLS tunnel. The `BearerSecurityScheme` scheme [24] makes use of a token that contains the access rights of a user and it is signed by the party responsible for the consumed service. One of the formats for the token is the JWT token [14].

III. A DESIGN FOR INTEROPERABILITY

This section discusses how to provide interoperability between Arrowhead and WoT, and it describes the SoS architecture for the ThingDirectory system.

A. Interoperating Arrowhead and WoT

The approach we advocate for is to provide a mechanism for a service consumer to find a thing by means of the Arrowhead framework, and to allow the two things to communicate with

¹<https://github.com/eclipse/thingweb.node-wot>

²<https://iot.mozilla.org/wot/>

```

{"title": "virtual-thermostat",
 "description": "A Thing corresponding
  to the thermostat in a room",
 "properties": {
  "temperature": {
  "type": "integer",
  "description": "Current temperature",
  "observable": true,
  "readOnly": true,
  "unit": "Celsius",
  "writeOnly": false,
  "forms": [
  {
  "href": "http://192.168.56.103:8081
  /virtual-thermostat/properties/temp
  erature",
  "contentType": "application/json",
  "op": [
  "readproperty"
  ],
  "htv:methodName": "GET"
  }
  ]
  },
  },
  ...
},
"security": [
  "nosec_sc"
],
"id": "urn:uuid:534e717d-65b6-44b4-9fa1
-56d4d5e75bce",
...
}}

```

Fig. 2. JSON encoding of a (partial) TD

each other by means of the WoT standard protocol. In our approach, the different properties and functions offered by a Thing are considered as services in the Arrowhead Framework. The Thing itself is considered as a System.

Within WoT, it is possible to discover things by sending a discovery request to the Thing Directory and retrieving a TD. This information should be obtainable via the Arrowhead framework, which receives information regarding available services through Service Registry and System Registry, and provides it back to service consumers via the Orchestrator.

Our approach considers a mapping between the TD and the information provided by the Arrowhead framework. Consider for example the excerpt from a TD in Fig. 2. Part of the information in the TD is related to the service interface, thus it does not pertain a place on the Arrowhead registries. On the other hand, information regarding how to reach the Thing deserves its place on the Service Registry. For example, Fig. 3 would represent the TD from Fig. 2 when the thing is registered on the Arrowhead framework, showing that the

```

{
  "endOfValidity": "",
  "interfaces": [ {
    "interfaceName" : "HTTP-INSECURE-JSON"
  } ],
  "metadata" : {
    "http-method" : "GET"
  },
  "providerSystem": {
    "address": "192.168.56.103",
    "authenticationInfo": "",
    "port": 8081,
    "systemName": "virtual-thermostat"
  },
  "secure": "NOT\_SECURE",
  "serviceDefinition": "get-temperature",
  "serviceUri": "/virtual-thermostat/prop
  erties/temperature",
  "version": 0
}

```

Fig. 3. JSON encoding of Arrowhead Service Registry's data for a Thing

webserver port 8081 from the TD is used as the port on which the Arrowhead service can be reached.

A more complete description of the virtual thermostat thing is depicted in Figure 4, which reports all the properties and actions exposed by the thing, and the services/verbs used in the Arrowhead context. By means of this approach, the virtual-thermostat thing becomes an Arrowhead system with the same name, and the different properties, temperature and targetTemperature are translated as readable services in Arrowhead, meaning that they are accessible using an HTTP GET operation. The actions decrement and setTemperature are designed as settable services meaning that it's possible to set their values using an HTTP POST requests.

A deeper discussion is needed with regards to security. In the previous example, the NoSecurityScheme scheme is translated into a not_secure Arrowhead level. On the other hand, it is important to consider how WoT and Arrowhead can interact with each other to harden their security options.

From the discussion in Section II, we can limit our analysis to HTTP and HTTPS communication, to not_secure, certificate and token Arrowhead security levels, and the NoSecurityScheme, BasicSecurityScheme and

Fig. 4. Translation from TD to Arrowhead

BearerSecurityScheme WoT schemes.

The usage of HTTP or HTTPS in WoT is reflected on Arrowhead’s interfaceName, which can be either HTTP-INSECURE-JSON or HTTP-SECURE-JSON. Regarding the security measures used for authentication, most of them are orthogonal to each other. With the exception of the token-based security, we can consider that the WoT service unique id provides information regarding the usage of NoSecurityScheme or BasicSecurityScheme, and in the latter case the service consumer will provide username and password on each request, e.g. in the HTTP headers. The Arrowhead certificate level can be used to harden the interaction, by requiring that the WoT interaction exploits a pre-installed Arrowhead-signed certificate to prove that the interaction is allowed.

A more interesting discussion is related to the BearerSecurityScheme WoT scheme and the Arrowhead token. In fact, we propose to use the JWT format on the WoT side, and allow the WoT token to be signed with the Arrowhead root certificates [16]. This way, the token used in WoT can be the token generated by the Arrowhead framework, leading to an inherent interoperability between Arrowhead and WoT security.

B. Architecture of the System of Systems

The ThingDirectory Arrowhead system exists in both the Arrowhead framework and in the WoT architecture, and it provides functionalities for the TD registration for the things that may be looked up through the Arrowhead local cloud.

The system administrator initiates the registration by contacting the ThingDirectory, which stores the TD. Based on the TD, the ThingDirectory system sends a request to an Arrowhead SystemRegistry for creating a “virtual” system that will act as a placeholder for the actual thing (Figure 5), and to the ServiceRegistry for creating the different services related to the newly created system. Those services will be available as regular services in the Arrowhead local cloud, taking advantage of the different core services’ functionalities.

IV. STRUCTURE OF THE THING DIRECTORY SYSTEM

This section details the implemented proof of concept for the Thing Directory system, and the interaction it has with other Arrowhead systems, as presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Arrowhead system as a placeholder for a WoT device

Fig. 6. ThingDirectory System Component diagram

The ThingDirectory system is built on three services (Register, Unregister, and Discover) as proposed in the Thing Directory architecture in the WoT standard [18].

The ThingDirectory System offers the ThingDirectory Register service to register the TDs for the things in a local cloud. The registration is performed using the URL provided by the thing for its TD. The System administrator initiates the registration by providing the URL to the ThingDirectory system, which will interact with SystemRegistry and ServiceRegistry to create placeholders for the actual thing (see Figure 5) and for its services, respectively. The ThingDirectory Unregister service is used to remove a TD from the Directory. When a TD is removed, the System registered for the thing and its services are also removed, as presented in Fig: 7. Periodically, a heartbeat is performed to check if a thing is still available. After 10 minutes of heartbeats timeout, the thing is considered unavailable, and the Unregister service is called automatically to perform the removal. The ThingDirectory Discover service allows to find the TD of a thing, for example to retrieve a list of all the TDs available in the local cloud.

Currently, the security implemented by the ThingDirectory is limited to mapping NoSecurityScheme and BasicSecurityScheme WoT schemes to Arrowhead’s not_secure Arrowhead level, and knowledge about the service will let the service consumer decide about using BasicSecurityScheme’s username and password or not. Moreover, we support the mapping between HTTP/HTTPS of WoT and HTTP-INSECURE-JSON / HTTP-SECURE-JSON Arrowhead interfaces.

V. USE CASE

In this section, we present a use case on which our approach has been applied.

Fig. 7. Thing deregistration

With the overarching goal of increasing energy efficiency, our home automation use case involves appliances and systems running on commodity hardware, and a Building Management System (BMS). The goal is to allow the BMS to control the appliances and systems remotely and independently from each other. The integration effort is made more interesting from the fact that some of the actors (Virtual thermostat and Smart LED) support the WoT standard, and the other ones are integrated into the Arrowhead framework.

Our main targets were a Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) subsystem, and a set of Smart LEDs that are used for lighting. We wanted to integrate the HVAC with a smart thermostat, to provide a better control of the strategies used to attain the best possible energy-efficient settings. Moreover, we wanted to save energy by turning the Smart LEDs on and off remotely when someone enters or leaves the room.

Our SoS was deployed in an apartment, where a Raspberry pi was connected to sensors to measure the temperature and the humidity. In the apartment there is also a set of Smart LEDs (Figure 8), and a computer with a virtual machine running an Arrowhead local cloud with its different core systems (not shown in the picture).

We have integrated our ThingDirectory system and generated the TD for all the things we have (Virtual thermostat and Smart LED). They were then registered through the

ThingDirectory and their systems and services made available on the Arrowhead local cloud. One of the systems was the temperature-controller (which is a placeholder for the virtual-Thermostat), offering two services, (i) Set-temperature, which is used to set the target temperature we want in the room and it is used by the HVAC to reach the desired temperature, and (ii) Get-temperature, which returns the current temperature in the room. With regards to the Smart LEDs set, we can control them in terms of switching them on and off. Together, these two efforts leads to the fully integration and interoperability that the use of our approach has enabled.

This use case will be improved to provide smart services to control the different things as part of the DomOS project, which aims to create an operating system for smart buildings. In this sense, DomOS requires mechanisms for controlling devices and appliances in residential settings, to help to maximize home security, bring flexibility for new devices, and improve appliances usage.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have proposed an approach to enable interoperability between the WoT and the Arrowhead framework. This has been done by designing an Arrowhead compliant system used to integrate things through their Thing Descriptions. Our approach has been showcased in a smart building use case where we successfully integrated an IoT virtual thermostat and

Fig. 8. Use case architecture

Smart LEDs into the Arrowhead framework to make them remotely controllable by the HVAC system.

Future work plans to improve the security of the scenarios by allowing to use Arrowhead's certificate security level, which will act on top of less secure WoT interactions, and by providing a mapping between Arrowhead's token security level and WoT's BearerSecurityScheme scheme. Investigations are under way regarding the computational feasibility of performing signature checks on the things, to verify Arrowhead's tokens.

An interesting concept related to the WoT is the Mashup [25], which is a distributed system made up of WoT devices. It is possible to generate code in the WoT Scripting API standard [20] from the sequence diagram of the interactions in the system. The generated code can then be deployed in a Mashup Controller to support the application logic by defining the Interaction Affordances employed in the distributed application. It can be argued that this approach is aligned with what the Orchestrator (see Section II-A) does in an Arrowhead environment, and future work can extend the WoT / Arrowhead interoperability to the level of Mashup / SoS.

Finally, this work allows an Arrowhead system to consume a WoT service, since the WoT protocol can be described by means of REST operations. To allow a WoT thing to consume an Arrowhead service, it would be necessary to provide an adapter that receives WoT requests and consume Arrowhead services, and this represents an ongoing work we are focusing on to further improve the interoperability of our solution.

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